

Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning

Designing a Just Participatory Process

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Agenda

Introduction

15 min

Workshop

60 min

Exit Survey
Poster

15 min

Key concepts: Participatory planning

“as a **collective** act and a moment, or a **series of** moments, in which **people** come together to **jointly** tackle a task and contribute to **shaping a place.**”

(Hofer & Kaufmann, 2022)

Hofer, K., & Kaufmann, D. (2022). Actors, arenas and aims: A conceptual framework for public participation. *Planning Theory*, 22(4), 357-379.

Key concepts: Spatial Justice

Distributive justice

Ensuring that the burdens and benefits of urban development are fairly distributed across the city

Recognition justice

Recognising difference and that different groups have different histories, aspirations, and needs

Procedural justice

Ensuring that spatial decision-making and procedures are inclusive and transparent

Key concepts: UP2030 Strategic Planning Cycle

Workshop: Goal

Create a **participatory process** to foster **spatial justice** in a specific case, combining the TU Delft **Strategic Planning Cycle** with the UP2030 participation tools

Workshop: Fictitious cases

A The municipality where you work wants to launch a new program to enhance the quality of existing public spaces while also mitigating climate risks, such as flooding and heat stress, through green and blue infrastructure. Participation of citizens and other local actors and stakeholders is a core value of the municipality.

Scale: City level

Type: Program

Possible tasks are:

- Meaningful community **engagement** to understand citizens' experiences and preferences for public spaces
- Map and understand the **local needs**, existing programs, and/or physical conditions of public areas
- Raise local **awareness** and build support
- Create a **vision** for the program
- Define possible **strategies** for the program and/or **policies** to support the program implementation

B The municipality where you work wants to redevelop and regenerate a former industrial area. Some participatory activities have already been conducted, and a collective vision for the area has been created. The vision is to transform the area into a mixed-use neighbourhood following a participatory approach based on prototyping and urban living labs.

Scale: Neighbourhood

Type: Redevelopment

Possible tasks are:

- Define place-based **strategies** and **policies**
- Co-design different **pilots and prototypes** to test innovative urban interventions (e.g., housing typologies, sustainable water systems, renewable energy, etc.)
- Implement pilots/prototypes in a living lab setting and evaluate their impact
- Define actions to upscale the pilots/prototypes to the rest of the area

Workshop: Instructions

Setting: Groups of 2 or 3 people

Case: You can work on your own case or a fictitious case we prepared for you

Materials

Planning Board + Case Template + Set of Cards

Timeline

- 10 min to get familiar with the case and cards
- 20 min to select and link the cards to the cycle
- 15 min to list spatial justice implications
- 15 min for collective reflection

Planning Board

Set of Cards

Case Template

Case description

Scale of intervention: Individual Neighbourhood Region
 Household/building City Other:

Type of intervention: Policy/program Infrastructure Behavioural
 Day/development Project Other:

Map the activities that need to be carried out

Spatial Justice Concerns

Allocating budget and resources to areas/groups that need the most
 Including citizens and local initiatives and businesses in the process
 Make sure the intervention fulfils the needs and preferences of marginalised groups
 Other: _____

Workshop: Tool cards

FRONT

Child & **Y**outh **F**riendly **U**rban **D**esign UP2030

Tool description

The Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD) tool summarizes the indicators of child-friendly cities. Based on CYFUD tailored toolkits are designed to the specific requirements of each project.

During UP2030, the tool was used to design toolkits for Belfast City Council and BKK-the Budapest Transport Centre, focusing on urban design qualities along children's routes to school and aiming to engage more children in active school travel initiatives.

Spatial Justice

Distributive Justice
The materials included in each CYFUD toolkit are flexible and available for each Municipality, local enablers and implementors to be used across different schools and communities in the pilot project that was designed for, and beyond.

Procedural Justice
Each CYFUD toolkit is developed in collaboration with the Municipality and local implementor to ensure that specific needs are addressed and local context is taken into consideration. A range of participatory activities ensures adaptability for different resources in each participating school or different projects.

Recognition Justice
CYFUD and its tailored toolkits recognize children's right to take part in urban design and planning processes. Through a range of child-friendly participatory tools and various modes of expression, they create space for children's experiences to be heard and to inspire policymaking decisions.

Description of the tool

Spatial Justice contributions

BACK

Child & **Y**outh **F**riendly **U**rban **D**esign UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

CYFUD includes participatory surveys to evaluate pilot projects and provide feedback for future programs

CYFUD inspires future urban design projects through community awareness & children's street design reflections

CYFUD is tailored to existing initiatives to ensure that local needs and priorities

CYFUD includes project roadmaps, campaign material & participatory tools to engage local enablers, schools and parents in designing safe routes to school

CYFUD supports children to assess, reflect and reimagine their route to school

CYFUD includes participatory tools to access and evaluate the impact of different strategy on creating safe routes to school

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Design Clips

Applications on the strategic cycle

Workshop: Tools overview

Neutrality Story Maps UP2030

Tool description
Neutrality Story Maps is a digital communication platform that fosters dialogue between citizens and policymakers on climate neutrality. Through map-based storytelling, it enables residents to share their experiences and aspirations, while helping city officials communicate climate challenges and engage communities in an accessible, narrative-driven format. By supporting two-way communication, the platform builds trust and promotes inclusive climate action.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
The platform addresses distributive justice by unveiling the concerns and hopes of marginalized communities, potentially leading to more equitable resource distribution and policy outcomes.
Through collaborative digital storytelling, city stakeholders are actively involved and empowered in developing the maps, fostering inclusivity and procedural justice.
The platform amplifies the voices of vulnerable groups and, by centering their lived experiences in urban adaptation planning, it contributes to the recognition justice dimension.

Digital Storytelling

Storytelling for Participatory Exchange UP2030

Tool description
The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology uses storytelling as a way to understand the concerns, ideas and desired futures of communities on chosen topics. It follows a 4-phase process that enables citizens to express their thoughts and feelings on their living environment and their desires for the future by telling imaginary stories that reflect real-life experiences. By analyzing the metaphors citizens use in their imaginary stories, we uncover deeper insights and use these to influence the design and deployment of real life interventions.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
The methodology includes an extended process of identifying and inviting participants from diverse communities, and amplifies their voices while maintaining a focus on consensus.
The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology supports procedural justice by enabling the orientation of policy and infrastructural design to citizen perspectives and preferences. By implementing early interventions can consider the ideas and narratives identified.
The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology promotes consensus between participants allowing for reflections on intersectional needs. The analytical procedure breaks down participant contributions, acknowledging individual perspective without platforming some voices over others.

Storytelling Workshop

Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design UP2030

Tool description
The Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD) tool summarizes the indicators of child-friendly cities. Based on CYFUD tailored tools, municipalities are designed to the specific requirements of each project.
During UP2030, the tool was used to design toolkits for Belfast City Council and BIK the Budgetary Transport Centre, focusing on urban design qualities along children's routes to school and aiming to engage more children in active school travel initiatives.

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The materials included in each CYFUD toolkit are flexible and available for each Municipality, local enablers and implementors to be used across different schools and communities in the pilot project that was designed for, and beyond.
Each CYFUD toolkit is developed in collaboration with the Municipality and local implementor to ensure that specific needs are addressed and local context is taken into consideration. A range of participatory activities ensure adaptability for different resources in each participating school or different projects.
CYFUD and its tailored toolkits recognize children's right to take part in urban design and planning processes. Through a range of child-friendly participatory tools and various modes of expression, they create space for children's experiences to be heard and to inspire policymaking decisions.

Children & Youth

Community Maps UP2030

Tool description
Community Maps is an interactive web platform for participatory planning, community engagement, and citizen science. It enables collaborative mapping without extra programming, supported by an admin tool for easy project setup. Municipalities can share planning proposals, such as cycle routes or green infrastructure, and gather public feedback directly through the platform. For example, Budgetary Transport Centre uses it to involve citizens in shaping its Green Infrastructure Strategy.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
Community Maps address distributive justice by enabling communities, especially those frequently left out of participatory planning processes, to identify areas of concern and opportunity so that sustainability interventions can be distributed in a fair and equitable manner.
Community Maps address procedural justice by enabling early, transparent engagement in planning processes, helping build trust and showing how communities can influence decisions. It also supports monitoring interventions through data and citizen feedback.
Community Maps address recognition justice through the co-production of data, sharing of lived experiences, priorities, and local insights that can shape and contextualize planning processes.

Mapping

UDCW Facilitation Toolkit UP2030

Tool description
The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools supporting knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context, facilitating communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge. The toolkit includes: Collaborative mapping; City visions and local needs matching; "A Day in the life" visioning exercise; and a 3D neighbourhood configurator tool. The tools are conceived to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens as well as with capacity building issues of public administrators and decision makers.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
Mapping the distribution of burdens and benefits across the city and groups
Identifying hotspots areas and setting priorities for interventions
Linking non-climate priorities to fair allocation of urban services and infrastructure
Highlighting intersectional injustices and vulnerabilities across different population groups
Participatory diagnosis and early engagement in planning
Ensuring feasibility of extended participatory activities
Digitizing and sharing results
Promoting climate interventions that also enhance urban quality
Guaranteeing fair representation of citizens in urban transformation processes
Co-producing and sharing data
Making visible existing injustices, exclusions, and marginalization
Understanding vulnerabilities and their root causes
Contextualizing climate design solutions with shared knowledge
Building collective storytelling and supporting recognition of diverse subjectivities

Design facilitation toolkit

Urban GEM UP2030

Tool description
The Urban Green Economy Model (UGEM) simulates the dynamics of various systems at the urban level. It covers main urban systems - buildings, transport, local energy supply, waste, water, local industry and services - including a new housing module.
With UGEM, decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios and generate evidence for budget allocation.
The model is under development with planned implementation in Thessaloniki.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
UGEM provides evidence to better distribute budget based on dynamic simulations of interconnected urban systems.
UGEM's findings can be used to support discussions with residents, experts, and decision-makers. It can also simulate citizen-informed policy scenarios via workshops to reflect local priorities, giving voice to the community on policy decisions.
UGEM can pay special attention to vulnerable groups. For example, with the housing module, energy poverty, energy efficiency and social housing investment needs, along with different policy actions can be assessed, to target investments where they are most needed.

Evidence-based decisions

Livable Cities Index UP2030

Tool description
The Livable Cities Index, created by CETAQIA, measures how good it is to live in a city. It uses 75 indicators in five areas: Society, Environment, Health, Land Use, and Resources. With public city data, it creates one overall score and ranking, but you can also see results by category. This helps identify what cities are doing well and where they can improve. In short: The Livable Cities Index turns complex data into a simple picture of city life and well-being.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
The index shows inequalities between cities, highlighting cities with less access to healthcare, green spaces, or services. This helps to focus actions where they are most needed, but its impact depends on local data and the city's commitment to act.
The index uses open data to make city planning more transparent and comparable. It helps to identify problems, guide actions, and track progress, but its impact depends on local capacity and citizen involvement to translate the index insights into suitable local interventions.
The index highlights social inequalities—like income gaps, vulnerable areas, or unemployment—while linking them to health and environmental risks. This helps cities recognize the specific needs of different communities and include them in urban planning.

Multidimensional index

Spatial Justice Benchmarking UP2030

Tool description
The Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJB) is a qualitative assessment framework that draws from justice theory and urban governance analysis. The tool is designed to evaluate how city strategic plans integrate spatial justice considerations by focusing on nine aspects linked to the three core dimensions of justice—distributive, procedural, and recognition. Each aspect can be assessed on a scale of low, starting, basic, growing, and embedded.
The tool was tested in 10 European Cities and the city of Rio de Janeiro via the analysis of their carbon-neutrality or sustainability plans.

Spatial Justice
HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED
Supports the assessment of three aspects related to distributive justice: (1) fair allocation of burdens and benefits, (2) access in terms of easy to reach urban services and amenities, and (3) people's ability to transform and make use of available services and amenities.
Supports the assessment of three aspects related to procedural justice: (1) how people and civic society influence decision-making, (2) how institutions are adapting to the diverse needs of the citizenry, and (3) how responsive are institutions to changes in the city (proactively or reactively).
Supports the assessment of three aspects related to recognition justice: (1) validation and recognition of difference in individuals and groups - dignified treatment of all, (2) support and implementation of alternative practices for that support marginalized groups, and (3) facilitation and respect for the co-existence of different groups.

Qualitative assessments

Create your own participatory planning process by integrating participation tools into the different planning phases

What are the implications for spatial justice?

Distributive Justice

Procedural Justice

Recognition Justice

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UP2030

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What are the implications for spatial justice?

Distributive Justice	Procedural Justice	Recognition Justice
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THANK YOU!

Social media:

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